

National-scale digital soil mapping performances are related to covariates and sampling density: Lessons from France

Azamat Suleymanov^{*}, Anne C. Richer-de-Forges, Nicolas P.A. Saby, Dominique Arrouays, Manuel P. Martin, Antonio Bispo

INRAE, Info&Sols, 45075 Orléans, France

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Soil
Modelling
Covariates
Spatial sampling
Digital soil mapping
Random forest

ABSTRACT

Accurate soil property and class predictions through spatial modelling necessitate a thoughtful selection of explanatory variables and sample size, as their choice greatly impacts model performance. Within the framework of Global Soil Nutrient and Nutrient Budget maps (GSNmap), the FAO Global Soil Partnership (GSP) launched a country-driven digital soil mapping (DSM) approach. The GSP asked the countries if they could implement the DSM prediction of ten soil properties, using their national point data and a set of widely available covariates (GSP_Cov). In this study, we examined the effect of including additional national-based covariates and soil observations on the performance of the prediction models using mainland France as a pilot. The learning soil dataset was based on a systematic 16-to-16 km grid. For a subset of soil properties, we also assessed using repeated k-fold cross-validation the effect of adding to this dataset many other irregularly spread measurements. The GSP_Cov included common widely available covariates that represented information about terrain, climate, and organisms. The second set of covariates consisted of the GSP_Cov, extended to extra covariates available at a national level, such as previously existing soil maps, geological maps, remote sensing products and others. Random Forest approach in combination with the Boruta selection method was employed for mapping ten soil properties: soil organic carbon (SOC), pH (water), total nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (P), available potassium (K), cation exchange capacity (CEC), bulk density (BD), and texture (clay, silt, and sand). The results revealed noteworthy enhancements in prediction performance for more than half of the properties, although, for some of them, the improvements were negligible. The most significant improvements were obtained for pH, CEC and texture, where geological variables and a previous pH map significantly contributed to the increase in accuracy. Adding numerous points (around 25,000) to the learning dataset improved the performance of soil particle-size fractions predictions. By broadening the spectrum of covariates and better covering the feature and geographical spaces considered in soil prediction models, this research underscores the importance of implementing a more diverse range of covariates at a national scale and of densifying soil information to enlarge the feature and geographical spaces of multidimensional soil/covariates combinations. This information should be taken into account in national and continental digital soil mapping endeavours.

1. Introduction

Soil plays a pivotal role in ecosystems, agriculture, and environmental management, making its accurate prediction and assessment an essential endeavour in the realm of Earth sciences. Soil mapping, along with densifying, storing, and harmonising soil data, is one of the topics of the new EU soil strategy for 2030 with the aim of bringing all EU soil ecosystems into good condition by 2050 (E.C, 2021; Arias-Navarro et al., 2023). Today soil cartography is primarily conducted using digital soil

mapping (DSM) approaches using the SCORPAN framework (McBratney et al., 2003). This framework involves integrating soil survey data, explanatory variables (covariates), advanced modelling and spatial interpolation techniques. Conventional soil mapping is a time-consuming and expensive process, making DSM a more suitable method, especially at a broad-scale (Arrouays et al., 2014).

In DSM field, the selection of explanatory variables is a pivotal step in achieving accurate and successful spatial predictions (Miller et al., 2015; Nussbaum et al., 2018; Wadoux et al., 2020). Depending on the scale of

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: azamat.suleymanov@inrae.fr (A. Suleymanov).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2024.e00801>

Received 19 February 2024; Received in revised form 17 April 2024; Accepted 18 April 2024

Available online 20 April 2024

2352-0094/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

the study area, the effectiveness of these variables may vary. In some cases, some covariates may be useless, or may even lead to misleading results (Wadoux et al., 2020). The choice of covariates in predictive modelling is thus a complex and critical decision, as it directly influences the model's ability to capture the underlying relationships between environmental factors and soil properties. This choice becomes even more crucial when attempting to achieve predictions at a national scale, where the heterogeneity of the landscape and the diversity of soil types can pose challenges. Moreover, at a national scale, accurate soil property prediction is essential to enable policymakers, farmers, and conservationists to make appropriate decisions, ultimately leading to more sustainable land use practices and more effective environmental management. Therefore, the choice of explanatory variables is an important step for spatial modelling.

Today, most DSM studies heavily depend on explanatory variables such as topography, climate data, and information derived from remote sensing data (Mulder et al., 2011; Chen et al., 2022). These variables are readily accessible and offer a wide range of spatial resolution, making them versatile for application across various scales. However, soil variations depend on many environmental factors, some of which may be missing in predictive models. This is especially the case for global predictions because some covariates are not available at a global scale. In addition, even at national scales, the availability of covariates may differ. Therefore, some studies do not include some important covariates, such as parent material, position, or soil information, though numerous studies reported a great influence of parent material or soil information in predicting soil properties and classes (Cahyana et al., 2023; Szatmári et al., 2021; Wiesmeier et al., 2011).

The number and density of soil points both in geographic and feature space also play a crucial role in DSM, influencing the accuracy and reliability of the generated soil maps. In addition to density, the coverage and representativeness of learning points should also be considered, both in geographic and feature space. A higher density of soil points enables a more detailed and comprehensive understanding of soil variability. However, increasing the number of points is always accompanied by additional time and financial costs, especially on a national scale. This raises the question of what sample size is sufficient. For instance, several studies have indicated that model accuracy is achieved up to a certain number of points, beyond which model improvement is marginal (Bouasria et al., 2023; Safaee et al., 2024).

Consequently, the optimal number of soil points depends on each study, while maintaining a balance between cost and labour intensity.

Within the framework of Global Soil Nutrient and Nutrient Budget maps (GSNmap), the FAO Global Soil Partnership (GSP) launched a country-driven DSM approach. The GSP asked the countries if they could implement the DSM prediction of ten soil properties, using their national point data and a DSM approach defined in a technical manual (Angelini et al., 2022) and using a set of widely available covariates (GSP_Cov).

This study aims to evaluate the performance in predicting these ten soil properties on a national scale, using France as a pilot area. Using the same training and statistical validation data and the same indicators of prediction performance, we examined the effect of adding national-based covariates to the GSP_Cov, as well as an additional set of soil observations. One objective is to assess what is the benefit of using a more extensive national set of covariates beyond the widely available GSP_Cov. We also aim to assess, compare and discuss the relative importance of variables generated by employing these two sets of covariates.

2. Methods

2.1. Soil data

As the first soil dataset, we used topsoil samples (0–30 cm) obtained from the French Soil Quality Monitoring Network (RMQS, Jolivet et al., 2006) (Fig. 1). The RMQS is a comprehensive environmental monitoring program in France designed to assess and monitor the quality of soil across the country. This program involves the collection of soil samples from 0 to 30 cm (or to the total depth of ploughed layer, hereafter named “topsoil”), and subsurface layers from approximately 30–50 cm (hereafter named “subsoil”) from various locations. The spatial sampling is based on a systematic random grid of 16 km by 16 km that covers metropolitan France (Jolivet et al., 2006). The analyses were conducted in laboratories to assess chemical, physical, and biological soil properties. In this study, ten topsoil properties, namely soil organic carbon (SOC, %), pH (water), total nitrogen (N, ppm), available phosphorus (P, ppm), available potassium (K, ppm), cation exchange capacity (CEC, cmol(c)/kg), bulk density (BD, g/cm³) and clay, silt, sand (%) were analysed. The number of georeferenced soil observations in the RMQS dataset was 2145 whatever the soil properties.

Fig. 1. RMQS (left) and GSM_F (right) soil observations (0–30 cm)

As an additional set of soil points, we utilized the dataset from the GlobalSoilMap-France (GSM_F) dataset (Mulder et al., 2016), which includes observations from the RMQS and the French Soil Inventory program (IGCS; Laroche et al., 2014). The IGCS dataset is aggregated from various studies in mainland France and is irregularly distributed, thus not tied to any systematic sampling scheme. The GSM_F dataset includes six properties intersecting with the GSNmap framework (pH, SOC, CEC and texture). The number of soil points in the GSM_F dataset was 29,128 for SOC, 27,162 for pH, 22,245 for CEC, 24,775 for clay, 24,826 for silt and 24,806 for sand.

2.2. Environmental covariates (GSP_Cov)

The GSP_Cov of environmental covariates represented relief, climate and organism variables (Appendix 1), i.e. the most widely available DSM variables. Terrain data included elevation (Yamazaki et al., 2017) and twelve commonly derived variables, including, slope, terrain wetness index and others. Climate data consisted of basic climate variables such as air temperature, land surface temperature, precipitation, evapotranspiration, wind, and snow cover derived from CHELSA (Climatologies at high resolution for the earth's land surface areas) and MODIS (Karger et al., 2017). Organism variables included the fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation (FAPAR), NDVI indices, growing season, land cover types, and MODIS short-wave infrared (SWIR) band. Thus, the GSP_Cov of covariates included terrain, climate, and organism as predictive variables in the SCORPAN model.

2.3. Environmental covariates (extra: added to GSP_Cov)

Table 1 shows the selected covariates (extra) added to GSP_Cov for DSM. Most of these extra covariates have been previously used for numerous DSM French studies, and detailed preparation steps can be found in (Martin et al., 2014; Meersmans et al., 2012; Mulder et al., 2016; Loiseau et al., 2019):

- 1) Soil types. The French soil map is composed of two types of soil Units: The SMU: Soil Mapping Units (UCS for Unités

Cartographiques de Sol in French) and the STU: Soil Typological Units (UTS for Unités Typologiques de Sol in French). The 1/1,000,000-scale Soil Geographical Database of France (i.e. based on European soil map) was used in this study (King et al., 1995). The STU is a soil typological unit (i.e., a concept of soil type/class according to a given classification/reference having specific and rather homogeneous properties). The STUs are most often not geographically delineated at 1/1,000,000 scale. The SMUs are geographical objects (often named “polygons” in geographical information systems) which are made up of one or more STUs. The dominant soil type on the SMU was used as a covariate (Loiseau et al., 2019) at the highest level of taxonomy (19 classes).

- 2) Soil texture (percentages of clay, silt, sand, grouped in five broad soil texture classes) maps were estimated from the 1:1,000,000 scale European Soil Geographical Database (King et al., 1995) and its associated pedotransfer rules available at <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-database-v2-raster-library-1kmx1km>. The dominant STU class of each SMU was retained and the centroid of its textural class was used to estimate clay, silt and sand values.
- 3) The 1/1,000,000-scale parent material map was produced as follows. The dominant soil parent material is stored in the 1/1,000,000 Geographical Soil Database of France (BDGSF, in French: “Base de Données Géographique des Sols de France”; King et al., 1995; INRA, 2018). This soil parent material was classified into 10 classes.
- 4) The soil pH map was produced using two sources (Martin et al., 2014). For the forest soils, the forest soil surface pH map (UMR-LERFOB, IFN, 2008) was used. This pH map of forest soils was produced by DSM, using relationships between understory vegetation and soil pH (UMR-LERFOB, IFN, 2008). For the other soils, the median pH per district from the national soil testing database was used (Lemercier et al., 2008).
- 5) Although GSP_Cov included land use types covariates, we expanded them to include a broader list. We used Corine Land Cover for four periods (1990, 2000, 2006 and 2018) (Feranec et al., 2010, 2016) and the ECOCLIMAP II database (Faroux et al., 2013). Thus, we included multiple versions for these covariates from different years to account for changes in land use types over time. Land uses were further reclassified into the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) land use classification (various crops, permanent grasslands, woodlands, orchards and shrubby perennial crops, wetlands, vineyards and others) (UE-SOeS, 2006). In addition, we used data from the French forest database (BDForest, IGN, version 1–2006, <http://professionnels.ign.fr/bdforet>). This database contains information about the predominant composition of plant species types, resulting in a more detailed classification.
- 6) Erosion rates map derived from Cerdan et al., 2010. Briefly, the map was generated by the following steps: firstly, a comprehensive database documenting erosion rates observed over short to medium-term periods across Europe was utilized. Then, an extrapolation of plot measurements to estimate regional erosion rates for land use types was performed.
- 7) Index of River Network Development and Persistence (IRNDP). IRNDP expresses the ability of the bedrock to induce water surface flowing or infiltration (BRGM, 2014).
- 8) Available water capacity map calculated by Wösten et al. (1999) pedotransfer function (Le Bas et al., 2004). This map was produced using the database of hydraulic properties of European soils (HYPRES) and the 1:1,000,000 Soil Geographical Database of Europe (Jamagne et al., 1994; King et al., 1995).
- 9) Geophysical gravimetric data, representing bouguer anomaly, free-air bouguer anomaly and bouguer gravity anomaly maps (Achache et al., 1997). The variations of the Bouguer anomaly are

Table 1
Selected extra covariates for DSM.

Variable	SCORPAN	Total rasters	Source
Clay, Silt and Sand	s	3	King et al., 1995
Forest types	o	10	Inventaire Forestier National, 2006
Corine land cover in 2000, 2006, 1990 and 2018	o	52	Feranec et al., 2010, 2016
Land use ECOCLIMAP II	o	11	Faroux et al., 2013
Erosion rates	s, r	1	Cerdan et al., 2010
Bouguer anomaly, free-air Bouguer anomaly and bouguer gravity anomaly	p	3	Achache et al., 1997
Ability of the bedrock to induce water surface flowing	p	1	BRGM, 2014
Parent material 1:1,000,000	p	10	King et al., 1995
Net Primary Production (max, min, mean, median and mode)	o	5	NASA LD, 2001
MrRTF	r	1	Gallant and Dowling, 2003
Soil pH map	s	1	Martin et al., 2014
Soil thickness, cm	s	1	King et al., 1995
Available water capacity	s	1	Le Bas et al., 2004
Soil type 1:1,000,000	s	19	King et al., 1995
Sentinel-2 A bands and spectral indices: parent material, soil, and NDVI time series indices	o	24	Loiseau et al., 2019

due to the sum of the gravity effect of the deep or distant basement, corresponding to the geological structures.

- 10) Soil thickness map (cm) derived from Soil Geographical Database of France (King et al., 1995) and pedotransfer rules (Hiederer, 2013; <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-data-base-derived-data>).
- 11) As an additional terrain variable, the multi-resolution of ridge top flatness (MrRTF) index was added (Gallant and Dowling, 2003). This index was previously reported to be an important predictor at a broad scale (Zeraatpisheh et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2022).
- 12) Complementary satellite data indices related to either parent material or soil were derived from Sentinel-2 mosaics (Loiseau et al., 2019). Three principal components of harmonized MODIS and PROBA-V normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) time series acquired in 2003 and 2016 were included, to represent intra-annual vegetation changes dynamics captured for very dry (2003) and a close to average climatic conditions (2016) year. Net Primary Production (NPP) maps were obtained from (Martin et al., 2011; NASA LD, 2001).

Thus, we expanded relief, climate and organism variables and we integrated new various covariates representing soil and parent material SCORPAN factors. Pre-processing of the covariates involved: 1) conversion of the coordinate system to EPSG:4326; 2) transforming and resampling of covariates into 250-m resolution, using a nearest neighbour interpolation for categorical, and bilinear interpolation for numerical variables; and 3) transforming categorical covariates (soil, parent material, land use) to dummy variables.

2.4. Feature selection of covariates

Feature selection of covariates was implemented through the Boruta feature selection technique for both datasets (Kursa and Rudnicki, 2010). This approach identifies the most relevant variables for building predictive models, often in the context of machine learning algorithms. Boruta operates in conjunction with a primary set of features and a shadow set of features. The primary set contains the original features that one wants to evaluate for their importance in making predictions, while the shadow set consists of randomly generated or permuted features that have no predictive power. The result is a subset of the most important features from the original primary set, selected based on their ability to improve the model's performance compared to random features. Boruta helps to mitigate overfitting by providing a robust feature selection process (Kursa and Rudnicki, 2010). It is especially useful when dealing with high-dimensional datasets, as it can enhance the generalization capability of a machine learning model by focusing on the most informative attributes.

2.5. Digital mapping

For digital mapping of soil properties, Random Forest (RF) algorithm was employed. Model tuning for each RF model was performed using hyper-parameters *mtry* (number of covariates to consider at any given split) and *splitrule* (splitting rule used during tree construction). The final set of hyper-parameters was chosen based on the lowest root mean squared error (RMSE) across the 10-fold cross-validation procedure with 10 repetitions. The outcomes of variables importance analysis were estimated using the function *varImp* and expressed in percentage (%).

2.6. Cross-validation

To evaluate the performance of RF models, a repeated 10-fold cross-validation approach was employed. This method partitioned the data into 10 non-overlapping subsets or "folds," with each fold serving as the statistical validation set once, while the remaining nine folds were used for calibrating the model. This process was repeated 10 times to ensure

comprehensive assessment and robustness of models.

To evaluate the predictive performance of models, we calculated several error metrics: mean error (ME), mean absolute error (MAE), RMSE, correlation coefficient (R), coefficient of determination (R^2) and Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency coefficient (NSE).

All steps to implement the RF algorithm, including model tuning, variable importance assessment and cross-validation were performed in the R programming environment using the "caret" package (Kuhn et al., 2023).

3. Results

3.1. Prediction performance metrics using both sets of covariates

Table 2 and Figs. 2 and 3 show the performance metrics of RF models using both datasets of covariates and soil observations. We found that the majority of properties predictions using the RMQS dataset showed better performances with the extra covariates, whereas, some improvements were negligible for other properties. The largest improvements were demonstrated for pH (RMSE = 0.93, R^2 = 0.51 using the first set of covariates, and RMSE = 0.8, R^2 = 0.63 when adding extra covariates), CEC (RMSE = 9.3, R^2 = 0.31 and RMSE = 8.2, R^2 = 0.47, respectively), clay (RMSE = 10.84, R^2 = 0.35 and RMSE = 9.84, R^2 = 0.47, respectively), silt (RMSE = 13.01, R^2 = 0.46 and RMSE = 12.47, R^2 = 0.5, respectively), and sand (RMSE = 17.6, R^2 = 0.43 and RMSE = 16.1, R^2 = 0.53, respectively). A very slight improvement of spatial predictions was reached for SOC, N, and K, whereas models for P content showed similar performances.

For the properties for which we were able to test the GSM_F dataset (Table 2), the results were only slightly different from those obtained by using RMQS only. Nevertheless, two consistent trends were observed.

- The RMSE of the predictions were always the lowest when using GSM_F as learning points and the GSP_Cov + extra dataset as covariates. Note, however, that the results of the other indicators of performance were often inconsistent with those of the RMSE.
- For the particle-size fractions predictions, almost all the indicators of performances were the best when using the same largest combination of learning and covariates datasets (i.e., GSM_F and GSP_Cov + extra).

3.2. Variable importance

Fig. 4 displays the variable importance for the top 10 covariates used by the models predicting each soil property when using the RMQS dataset as learning soil data and the GSP_Cov + extra datasets as covariates.

As expected, the soil pH map extra covariate highly contributed to pH prediction. In addition, the model included several extra variables (NDVI, maxNPP, calcareous rocks, forest type) in the top 10 predictors. Note, however, that the contribution of the soil pH map largely dominated those of the other co-variables.

Among extra variables, only the forest area was included in the model to predict SOC content. The presence of only one new covariate from the extra set explains why we did not observe a strong improvement in the SOC prediction performances (Table 2).

Interestingly, the extra-added land use types contributed a lot to the prediction models for P and K. Eight of the ten main factors explaining the variation of P content were related to land use, half of which were from the extra covariates. The K model used one extra land use covariate as the most important, followed by several extra covariates in the top ten, among which calcareous rocks, spectral indices related to either parent material or soil (geological response (gypsym, silt) and clay index), forest area, and Cambisol.

Among additional covariates, the bouguer gravity anomaly contributed a factor for BD modelling. For the CEC model, six extra variables,

Table 2

Mean of the prediction performance metrics after repeated 10-fold statistical cross-validation procedure with 10 repetitions (bold numbers show the best result).

Property	Covariate	Soil data set	ME	MAE	RMSE	R	R ²	MEC
pH	GSP_Cov	RMQS	0	0.75	0.93	0.71	0.51	0.5
	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	0	0.63	0.8	0.8	0.63	0.63
	GSP_Cov	GSM _F	0.01	0.61	0.78	0.75	0.56	0.56
SOC	GSP_Cov + extra	GSM _F	0	0.56	0.73	0.78	0.62	0.61
	GSP_Cov	RMQS	-0.03	0.96	1.54	0.65	0.43	0.43
	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	-0.03	0.93	1.51	0.67	0.45	0.45
N	GSP_Cov	GSM _F	-0.04	0.71	1.25	0.56	0.31	0.31
	GSP_Cov + extra	GSM _F	-0.04	0.7	1.23	0.57	0.32	0.32
	GSP_Cov	RMQS	-24	759.08	1169.22	0.65	0.42	0.42
P	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	-15.3	731.66	1139.23	0.67	0.45	0.45
	GSP_Cov	RMQS	-1.61	30.37	49.82	0.49	0.24	0.24
	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	-1.57	29.97	49.81	0.49	0.24	0.24
K	GSP_Cov	RMQS	-9.29	171.85	315.84	0.33	0.11	0.1
	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	-9.54	169.01	315.02	0.35	0.12	0.12
	GSP_Cov	RMQS	0	0.14	0.19	0.55	0.3	0.3
BD	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	0	0.14	0.19	0.57	0.32	0.32
	GSP_Cov	RMQS	-0.21	6.72	9.3	0.56	0.31	0.3
	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	-0.15	5.62	8.2	0.68	0.47	0.46
CEC	GSP_Cov	GSM _F	-0.22	4.37	6.19	0.63	0.4	0.39
	GSP_Cov + extra	GSM _F	-0.2	4.19	5.97	0.66	0.44	0.43
	GSP_Cov	RMQS	-0.18	8.12	10.84	0.59	0.35	0.33
Clay	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	-0.17	7.14	9.84	0.68	0.47	0.45
	GSP_Cov	GSM _F	-0.27	6.66	9.21	0.68	0.46	0.45
	GSP_Cov + extra	GSM _F	-0.25	6.33	8.88	0.7	0.49	0.49
Silt	GSP_Cov	RMQS	-0.03	10.49	13.01	0.68	0.46	0.45
	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	-0.04	9.83	12.47	0.71	0.5	0.49
	GSP_Cov	GSM _F	0.01	9.03	11.5	0.75	0.56	0.55
Sand	GSP_Cov + extra	GSM _F	-0.01	8.72	11.18	0.76	0.58	0.57
	GSP_Cov	RMQS	-0.2	14.56	17.96	0.65	0.43	0.41
	GSP_Cov + extra	RMQS	-0.16	12.66	16.1	0.73	0.53	0.52
	GSP_Cov	GSM _F	-0.25	11.65	15.08	0.74	0.55	0.54
	GSP_Cov + extra	GSM _F	-0.21	11.05	14.47	0.77	0.59	0.58

Where GSP_Cov = worldwide available covariates provided by GSP-FAO; GSP_Cov + extra = GSP_Cov + plus French national extra covariates; RMQS = systematic 16 to 16 km grid of soil properties. GSM_F = RMQS + about 25, 000 irregularly spread points from the IGCS dataset.

Fig. 2. RMSE values for each fold in 10-fold cross-validation procedure using the RMQS dataset as learning points and 1) the GSP_Cov of covariates (in red) or 2) the GSP_Cov + extra set of covariates (in blue).

Fig. 3. R^2 values for each fold in 10-fold cross-validation procedure using the RMQS dataset as learning points and 1) the GSP_Cov of covariates (in red) or 2) the GSP_Cov + extra set of covariates (in blue).

namely, soil pH map, calcareous rocks, crystalline rocks and migmatites, NDVI variability, geological response and clay spectral indices were included in the top 10 predictors. Note that many covariates were the same for CEC and clay content prediction, which is logical.

For soil texture, we expectedly found a large influence of soil properties (texture, pH) and parent material maps. Soil pH map mostly contributed to the model for mapping clay content, in addition to calcareous rocks, geological response and clay spectral indices. Note that none of the texture covariates derived from the 1:1,000,000 scale soil map had high importance for clay prediction. Among the extra covariates, we observed a very large importance of the bouguer gravity anomaly variable for silt content, then followed by silt, soil pH, crystalline rocks and migmatites and available water capacity raster. For sand modelling, all three soil texture-derived fractions were among the top 10 important co-variates.

3.3. Predicted maps and their differences

Fig. 5 shows the predicted maps using the input RMQS data and both covariate sets, as well as differences among the produced maps. In general, the spatial patterns were rather similar. The maps with the same level of accuracy were quite indistinguishable (SOC, P, K, BD), though some slightly higher values of K were found in some calcareous soils. Conversely, the pH, CEC and soil texture maps were more discernible due to the influence of the extra variables on the spatial modelling and its accuracy. The pH map showed a higher and expected contrast between very calcareous areas such as Champagne and Charentes in the west of France, the Alsace plain in the northern east, calcareous areas in the south-east, and very acid areas such as sandy podzols under forest in the Landes of Gascony region in the south-west and the Vosges mountains in the north-east.

The clay and CEC maps were also much more contrasted when using the GSP_Cov + extra dataset than when using the GSP_Cov set only. Some patterns reflected the importance of some parent materials the

alteration of which generally results in clayey soils or sandy soils. As CEC measurements were conducted using the cobalt hexamine method (Ciesielski et al., 1997), the pH map covariate contributed largely to revealing a better contrast between sandy acidic soils and clayey calcareous derived soils. Clay and sand maps exhibited also a higher and more consistent contrast when using the GSP_Cov + extra covariates. The effect of pH can be considered as an indirect effect, i.e., pH is higher in calcareous-derived soils the weathering of which often produces clay particles, and is, in turn, lower in crystalline and migmatites rocks, the weathering of which often produces sand particles. Interestingly, the dominant soil texture derived from the 1:1,000,000 soil map also contributed and helped to better capture some extreme values of well-known very sandy soils such as the Podzols of the Landes of Gascony (e.g., Augusto et al., 2010; Richer-de-Forges et al., 2017). The contribution of the remote sensing-derived clay index to the clay prediction when using GSP_Cov + extra covariates confirms the interest in remote sensing for improving clay mapping at the French mainland scale (Loiseau et al., 2019; Richer-de-Forges et al., 2023a). Surprisingly, the two silt maps were rather consistent though variable importance showed that six extra covariates, among which the top three, were included in the model based on the GSP_Cov + extra dataset. Overall, the maps of clay, silt and sand were consistent with previous work from Caubet et al. (2019).

The maps showed noticeable differences among both sets of covariates that were more contrasted when their performances were different (Fig. 5). Since the pH and CEC maps with additional variables exhibited higher performances, the difference between them and the maps using the GSP_Cov set was readily evident. The differences in values reached up to ± 2 units of soil pH and 20 cmol(c)/kg of CEC. The map using the GSP_Cov clearly overestimated the low pH values mainly located under forested acid soils, whereas it underestimated the high pH values mainly located on agricultural calcareous soils. The SOC maps showed a slight overestimation of the map using only the GSP_Cov in the forested mountainous areas.

Fig. 4. Variable importance (%) of the top 10 covariates from the GSP_Cov + extra dataset; green barplots show the extra covariates and blue barplots show the GSP_Cov covariates used in both GSP_Cov and GSP_Cov + extra datasets; RMQS is the learning points dataset.

The map of BD differences showed small noticeable patterns in the south-central region. Interestingly, when considering a given set of covariates, the maps of clay content and CEC were consistent. Conversely, if we look at the maps of the differences attributable to the adding of new covariates, the maps show that, compared to the GSP_Cov + extra based map, the map using the GSP_Cov set alone exhibits a trend to overestimate low values and to underestimate high values. Considering our knowledge of the French soils, the very long history of soil mapping in France (Arrouays et al., 2021) and the very large amount of data gathered and rescued from previous conventional soil surveys

(Arrouays et al., 2017), we can state that the GSP_Cov set alone, induces a very strong smoothing of the maps, which is not reflecting the reality. Interestingly too, the silt and sand maps showed a couple of different symmetrical patterns of high differences, which suggests that over- and under-estimations of these two fractions are symmetrically linked. Obviously, some large patterns of differences are linked to errors made when modelling using the GSP_cov covariates only and corrected when the extra covariates are added. Among nutrients, N and K maps showed a prominent divergence, where the maximum differences reached 4000 and 40 ppm, respectively. The patterns of the map of N differences were

Fig. 5. Maps produced using RMQS as the set of soil learning variables and; 1) the GSP_Cov set of covariates; 2) the GSP_Cov + extra set of covariates; and 3) differences between the two sets of covariates. The difference is calculated as the predicted values obtained using the first set of covariates (GSP_Cov) minus the predicted values obtained using the second set of covariates (GSP_Cov + extra).

Fig. 5. (continued).

Fig. 5. (continued).

very similar to those of the 1:1,000,000 soil map. For N, the very large differences close to -4000 ppm closely correspond to the very local presence of Andosols.

4. Discussion

4.1. Additional covariates effect on prediction performance

The results of our study revealed a trend where the inclusion of additional covariates to the GSP_Cov set consistently led to improved predictions for about half of the soil properties. This improvement can be attributed to the fact that these supplementary variables captured additional information related to the distribution of the soil properties. This information may be causal (for instance, the effects of some land use or the effect of some parent materials) or simply correlated to the spatial distribution of the predicted properties.

Earlier, [Martin et al. \(2014\)](#) used several sets of covariates for a map of SOC stocks in France. The first set included land use types and clay; the second set included the above-mentioned variables plus soil types, climate, temperature, soil moisture mineralization modifiers, and NPP. Maps of pH, parent material and organic matter additions, were incorporated into a third set as extra variables. The results from Martin et al. showed that adding a second set of variables to the first improved the performance remarkably, whereas the third set did not have a strong impact.

Similarly, [Zhou et al. \(2021\)](#) tested various sets of covariates for mapping SOC and soil carbon-to-nitrogen ratio (C:N) in Switzerland. The authors developed the following five experimental models: using single Landsat-8 (Model I), Sentinel-2 (Model II) and Sentinel-3 data (Model III), as well as climate and terrain variables together (Model IV), and all above-mentioned predictors (Model V). They achieved the best accuracy predictions for both soil parameters using Model V. This is

consistent with the research by [Azizi et al. \(2022\)](#), who also used four different scenarios for digital mapping of heavy metals in western Iran: 1) remote sensing alone; 2) remote sensing + terrain; 3) remote sensing + terrain + thematic maps; and 4) remote sensing + terrain + thematic maps + soil properties. The last scenario, which included all explanatory variables, was the most efficient for predicting heavy metals concentration.

Though our study and the above-mentioned ones suggest that increasing the number of covariates may be beneficial for DSM, we should be very cautious about the relevance of this message. Increasing the number of co-variates makes sense only if they bring relevant information, and if this information is not already included in previously existing covariates. Including irrelevant covariates may result in statistically acceptable performances for irrelevant maps ([Wadoux et al., 2020](#)). We should keep in mind that the covariates must make sense from a soil science point of view. The selection of covariates should lead to keeping only relevant ones, and minimizing redundancy (as we did, for instance using Boruta), remembering the following principle stated by [Arrouays et al. \(2020\)](#): “Machine-learning methods are to be used with caution with respect to their interpretability and parsimony”.

Finally, we should look at the maps, and assess if they make sense from a geographical and pedological point of view. In the present study, we compared two DSM sets of predictions using statistics calculated on the whole map performances. We also mapped their differences and used visual interpretation and expert knowledge. This method is obviously subjective as it relies on the expert's knowledge of soil geography. Therefore, this is a limitation of our study. Ways forward less subjective comparisons have been proposed by [Rossiter et al. \(2022\)](#), who compared spatial patterns from two DSM prediction maps and from detailed field surveys in the US. In addition to mapping differences and applying a visual assessment, they suggested comparing the spatial continuity of maps using geostatistics. They also suggested a set of

numerical methods to compare spatial patterns between maps. Among these methods are the use of the “V-measure” (Nowosad and Stepinski, 2018; Nowosad, 2021) and “landscape-level metrics” (Uuemaa et al., 2013; McGarigal et al., 2012). We acknowledge that we could have implemented a deeper analysis of the differences between maps using these methods. However, the objective of the present study was not to analyse in detail how the maps were consistent in capturing all spatial patterns. In addition, the final assessment of a DSM prediction relies on what the experts consider the “truth” or the most “accurate” soil map (detailed field surveys, in the case study by Rossiter et al. (2022)). In our case, this assessment of spatial patterns would have needed a “reference” soil map detailed enough and considered reliable. As even the 1:250,000 conventional soil map of France is not yet complete over the whole territory we decided not to implement these methods, and we focused on some obvious and large discrepancies using our knowledge of the French soil geography.

4.2. Importance of covariates

Several extensive reviews of DSM identified the most influential covariates for each property at broad scales (Chen et al., 2022; Lamichhane et al., 2019). For instance, the spatial distribution of SOC and SOC stocks was shown to be mainly controlled by climate (temperature, precipitation), elevation, land use and vegetation, and parent materials. This has been confirmed in previous SOC mapping studies in mainland France (Mulder et al., 2016). In another study, a clay map was reported as the most important variable for explaining the spatial patterns of SOC concentration (Pahlavan-Rad et al., 2018). Indeed, when the controlling factors of organic carbon inputs to soil are rather similar, the other side of SOC balance in soil depends on the mineralization rates of organic matter, which are in part controlled by clay content and mineralogy (e.g., Six et al., 2002; Lavalley et al., 2020). However, in our study, among the additional covariates, only the forest type variable was included in the top 10 list.

Climate variables (precipitation and temperature), parent materials, land use and vegetation, and soil type are the main factors determining soil pH levels (Chen et al., 2019, 2022; Suleymanov et al., 2024). In our study, we demonstrated a significant improvement in pH predictions by adding a soil pH map, which was expected. The usefulness of accompanying maps of soil parameters was demonstrated in DSM studies (e.g., Dong et al., 2019). For instance, Tziachris et al. (2019) showed that some soil parameters used as covariates (clay, electric conductivity, pH) had more influence for predicting soil organic matter (SOM) than the environmental variables. Similarly, Møller et al. (2023) included maps of soil texture, SOM and soil drainage classes for modelling oxalate-extractable aluminium (Al_o) and iron (Fe_o).

Among nutrients, N content was mainly controlled by elevation and climate (snow cover, temperature, precipitation). The results reported by Zhou et al. (2020), showed that elevation, by a significant margin, was the leading variable controlling soil total N in Central Europe. Note that at rather high elevations, elevation and climate data are often strongly correlated especially in France (Jamagne, 2011). Nevertheless, our extra explanatory variables as forest and soil types (Cambisol) also contributed to the predictions of the N model. Various land use types were the most influencing predictors for P and K distribution. Six additional variables were included in the top 10 covariates for K modelling, among which were land use types (croplands, forest type), calcareous rocks, spectral indices related to either parent material or soil, and Cambisol. Earlier, Hengl et al. (2021) reported climate as the most important covariate for DSM of nutrients in Africa. Of course, French agricultural soils receive much more nutrient inputs than African soils. Therefore, we assume in our study that the influence of land use types on nutrients (P and K) was largely attributable to fertilization (mineral or organic), cattle breeding and pastures, and crop rotations.

The combined variable importance analyses revealed that vegetation and climate were the most important covariates for mapping BD, which

was consistent with other regional and national-scale studies (Chen et al., 2022). The bouguer gravity anomaly variable was also included in the top 10 predictors of BD among additional covariates. CEC concentrations were closely related to soil pH, because the higher the acidity the more negatively charged the colloids are (Gavrilescu, 2014). For this reason, the major controlling factors of CEC spatial variability were similar to those controlling pH. Among the covariates, the soil pH map was the most important, followed by calcareous rocks, which have a strong effect on soil alkalinity (Pastore et al., 2022).

Six extra covariates were included in the silt and sand models, and five for mapping clay content, representing other soil parameters and parent materials. Soil pH map was the most important extra predictor for clay and sand, and was included in the top 10 variables for the silt model. Soil pH is an important soil chemical property which controls many soil properties. However, one should not conclude that soil pH controls particle-size distributions of French soils. Indeed, pH is often negatively correlated with clay content (Gruba and Socha, 2016). For example, Pahlavan-Rad and Akbarimoghaddam (2018) investigated the spatial distribution of soil texture fractions and pH in a flood plain of eastern Iran. They found similar spatial patterns of clay, sand and pH, because an increase in clay content increased the susceptibility of soils to sodic conditions in saline soils. Indeed, pH is correlated with many parameters, among which clay content and CEC, because clay content and CEC control the soil buffering capacity and the ability of soil to adsorb and release some cations that can maintain high pH values (Ca⁺⁺, Mg⁺⁺, Na⁺) or very low pH values (Al⁺⁺⁺). Thus, soil pH maps are, of course, useful for predicting pH, but these maps also integrate other information that can be helpful to improve the prediction performance of other parameters that are correlated to soil pH (e.g., texture, CEC).

Parent material is one of the key predictors for spatial modelling of soil texture, which was shown both in the review article by Chen et al. (2022) and several national studies (e.g., Mulder et al., 2016; Viscarra Rossel et al., 2015). Earlier mapping of soil texture in France also showed patterns of clay, silt and sand distribution associated with parent materials (Caubet et al., 2019; Loiseau et al., 2019, 2020), which were comparable to the current results. For example, we showed that sand and crystalline parent materials, as well as calcareous parent materials, were important for the clay content prediction. The calcareous parent material effect on clay might come from causal relationships because, under the French climate, the weathering of most calcareous parent materials results in clayey soils (Jamagne, 2011). Conversely, the relationships with sand and crystalline parent material might be due to less clay in their weathering products and/or to the fact that clay and sand contents are negatively correlated. The bouguer gravity anomaly map was the most influential covariate for the silt predictions. We interpret this result as an effect of large areas of very deep loess deposits in northern France, together with a very flat and low-elevation topography (Antoine et al., 2003). Bouguer anomaly covariates can reveal areas with distinct geological or topographic features, such as rock density and abrupt changes in topography (Choi et al., 1999; Lo et al., 2023). So, we strongly recommend the incorporation of lithological or geological variables for DSM of numerous parameters (Rossiter, 2023).

Overall, we should stress the large importance of the soil pH map for predicting many properties. We already discussed the reasons (causal or simple correlation) why this map had such a dominant effect on some predictions. We should stress that although this map was used as a covariate, it does not have the same status as the other ones. To draw this map, the authors used two distinct sources of information. Under forest and natural vegetation, pH mapping was achieved using correlations between vegetation-derived indicators and pH (UMR-LERFOB, IFN, 2008). To establish these relationships, a set of soil pH measurements was used to calibrate a predictive model. Under other land uses, soil pH was mapped by aggregating hundreds of thousands of topsoil pH measurements at administrative levels. These sources of pH measurements were independent of the RMQS data that we used to calibrate our models. However, we should stress that many soil measurements were

used to build this pH covariate. Most of these measurements were not precisely georeferenced, which explains why they were aggregated in administrative units (Saby et al., 2017). However, we should recognize that the pH map conveys much more information based on soil measurements than the other covariates. One may wonder if, for mapping pH, it would have been more effective to incorporate this soil information on pH as a basic point information for learning, than as a covariate map. This would have needed to generate point based proxys of pH values (for instance by areal to point kriging, e.g., Román Dobarco et al., 2016) from administrative statistics. This possibility is worth considering, but it is outside the scope of the present study.

4.3. Effects of increasing the learning set of soil properties measurements and the number of covariates

In this study, increasing the number of covariates helped to improve the feature space coverage and representativeness. The effect of adding new covariates on prediction performance was more pronounced than the effect of increasing the number of points. However, we showed that, for a couple of soil properties, adding a large amount of GSM_F point data (from about 20,000 to 25,000) to the RMQS regular soil grid (about 2000 points) led to a slight improvement in the RMSE. Most importantly, for sand, silt and clay content, we observed slight but systematic improvements in almost all of the indicators of the prediction performance. We may attribute these slight improvements to better coverage of the feature space (both for soil properties and covariates) when adding the GSM_F dataset. In our case, only the improvement of feature coverage possibly led to prediction improvement since the prediction model does not include spatial interpolation. This improvement of the feature coverage contributes to the effective estimation of regression parameters and ensures that the validity domain of the predictions is correct (Hengl et al., 2003; Biswas and Zhang, 2018). One of the main advantages of the RMQS grid is its homogeneous coverage of the geographical space. Conversely, one pitfall of this grid is the rather large distance between points (16 km or more). As RMQS is a subset of GSM_F, the ranges of soil properties and covariates values are larger than when using RMQS alone. Therefore, GSM_F helped to capture more soil property values and covariate combinations that the RMQS grid may have missed. As such, it enabled to capture the variability of the soil and environmental properties (Biswas and Zhang, 2018). Blackford et al. (2022) proposed to use uncertainty guided additional sampling to improve digital soil map accuracy. This was not the case in the present study, where we just added new available samples. However, adding a large number of more clustered points helped to capture more local variability. Though less striking than expected, these results are consistent with the recommendations drawn by Voltz et al. (2020), who proposed two strategies of new data acquisition for the future of DSM in France: (i) Increasing the density of soil profiles for France and, (ii) promoting detailed mapping of reference areas, representative of local soil patterns.

In the present study, the interest in strategy (i) was demonstrated by the better performances of the predictions when using GSM_F, especially for particle-size fractions. Of course, if affordable, adding points the location of which would be selected by a relevant sampling strategy would enable more efficiency (e.g., Minasny and McBratney, 2006, 2016; Brus and Heuvelink, 2007; Vašát et al., 2010; Szatmári et al., 2019; Wadoux et al., 2019). The strategy (ii) would be beneficial, not only by increasing the number of soil point data but also by restricting the modelling to areas that have specific geographical patterns and controlling factors of the spatial distribution of soil properties. This will enable to development of more local models, and avoid increasing the well-known smoothing effect induced by DSM models, especially when calibrated over broad-scale areas (Bishop et al., 2015; Tifafi et al., 2018; Arrouays et al., 2020; Richer-de-Forges et al., 2023b). In this way, adhering to these two strategies will be beneficial for future DSM research in France.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we assessed the impact of incorporating additional covariates beyond a commonly used set proposed to map ten soil properties of the world using a DSM country-based bottom-up approach. We ran a pilot study for mainland France. In this pilot study, we added to this common set some extra national-based covariates, such as maps of soil classes and properties, parent materials, spectral bands and indices, as well as time-series land use types. Employing Random Forest method along with the Boruta selection technique, we mapped the following ten soil properties: soil organic carbon (SOC), pH (water), total nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (P), available potassium (K), cation exchange capacity (CEC), bulk density (BD), and texture (clay, silt, and sand) in mainland France. The results demonstrated improvements in prediction performance for about half of the properties, with the most significant enhancements observed in the prediction of pH, CEC, and texture. For these properties, geological variables and a previous pH map played a pivotal role in increasing the prediction performance of the DSM models. Furthermore, the maps generated with the expanded set of variables gave a more contrasted and expected range of results. They were also more credible when assessed by local experts and/or compared to local studies and knowledge. This research underscores the importance of incorporating a broader spectrum of covariates in soil prediction models on a broad scale, emphasizing the need to test and incorporate more SCORPAN variables on the condition that they bring relevant information and that these added variables are not redundant with previously existing covariates. The results also stress that having a deep look into maps, into their spatial patterns, contrast, and ranges of predicted soil properties, are crucial steps to assess the relevance of the spatial predictions. Adding a large number of learning points slightly improved the predictions of some properties. Though the geographical space is reasonably covered by an existing systematic grid in France, adding more points helped to capture more variations in the feature space, resulting in prediction performance improvements. As we strive to improve our understanding of soil ecosystems and their dynamics, it is worth considering the potential of an expanded suite of covariates, as well as increasing the number of soil observations. The covariates selection should rely on their relevance and their potential to improve predictions and avoid overfitting. Adding more points of soil information should both help to densify the geographical coverage and expand the feature coverage. The assessment of the resulting maps should involve, not only calculating statistical indicators of the prediction performance but also looking at maps from soil science and soil geography points of view. Adopting this approach represents a promising avenue for advancing the accuracy and applicability of soil property predictions, with potential implications for sustainable land management and environmental conservation.

Funding

European Joint Program for SOIL “Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils” (EJPSOIL) funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 862695).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Azamat Suleymanov: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Anne C. Richer-de-Forges:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology. **Nicolas P.A. Saby:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Data curation. **Dominique Arrouays:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Data curation. **Manuel P. Martin:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Antonio Bispo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The soil properties maps produced using the RMQS dataset and "GSP_Cov" set of covariates are openly accessible: <https://doi.org/10.57745/3QFT2T>. The RMQS dataset is available: <https://doi.org/10.15454/QSXKGA>.

Acknowledgements

This research was developed in the framework FAO Global Soil Nutrient and Nutrient Budget maps (GSNmap) organized by FAO Global Soil Partnership and has benefited from ongoing discussions within WP6 (Soil data & Reporting) of the European Joint Program for SOIL "Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils" (EJP SOIL) funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 862695).

A.C. Richer-de-Forges is chair, and D. Arrouays, M.P. Martin and N.P. A. Saby are members of the "Centre d'expertise Scientifique Theia - Cartographie Numérique des Sols." supported by the CNES.

Most of the French point soil data has been collected or rescued thanks to funding from the national 'Groupement d'Intérêt Scientifique Sol' involving the French ministries in charge of agriculture and the environment, the French Agency of the ecological transition (ADEME - l'Agence de la transition écologique), the French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE - Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement), the French National Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD - l'Institut de recherche pour le développement), the French Geological Survey (BRGM - Service géologique national), and the French National Institute of Geographic and Forest Information (IGN - l'Institut national de l'information géographique et forestière). In most cases, these national fundings were complemented by French Regions or more local agencies and organizations. We thank all the people involved in sampling the sites and populating the French DoneSol database. We thank the people involved in maintaining and improving the structure and the accessibility of DoneSol.

Appendix 1. First set of covariates (GSP_Cov).

Temperature	Resolution, m
Mean air temperature (annual)	
Mean daily temperature of warmest month	1000
Mean daily temperature of coldest month	1000
Precipitation	
Mean annual precipitation	1000
Mean precipitation of wettest month	1000
Mean precipitation of driest month	1000
Mean monthly precipitation of wettest quarter	1000
Mean monthly precipitation of driest quarter	1000
Potential evapotranspiration	
Mean monthly PET	1000
Minimum monthly PET	1000
Range monthly PET	1000
Maximum monthly PET	1000
Wind	
Minimum monthly wind speed	1000
Maximum monthly wind speed	1000
Range monthly wind speed	1000
Growing season	
Number of days with mean daily air temperature above 10 degrees Celsius	1000

(continued on next column)

(continued)

Temperature	Resolution, m
Vegetation indices (NDVI)	
Mean March–May from 2000 to 2022	250
Mean June–August from 2000 to 2022	250
Mean September–November from 2000 to 2022	250
Mean December–February from 2000 to 2022	250
Standard deviation March–May (2000–2022)	250
Standard deviation June–August (2000–2022)	250
Standard deviation Sept.-Nov. (2000–2022)	250
Standard deviation Dec.-Feb. (2000–2022)	250
Fraction of photosynthetically active radiation (FPAR)	
Mean March–May from 2000 to 2022	500
Mean June–August from 2000 to 2022	500
Mean September–November from 2000 to 2022	500
Mean December–February from 2000 to 2022	500
Standard deviation March–May (2000–2022)	500
Standard deviation June–August (2000–2022)	500
Standard deviation Sept.-Nov. (2000–2022)	500
Standard deviation Dec.-Feb. (2000–2022)	500
Land surface temperature day	
Mean March–May from 2000 to 2022	1000
Mean June–August from 2000 to 2022	1000
Mean September–November from 2000 to 2022	1000
Mean December–February from 2000 to 2022	1000
Standard deviation March–May (2000–2022)	1000
Standard deviation June–August (2000–2022)	1000
Standard deviation Sept.-Nov. (2000–2022)	1000
Standard deviation Dec.-Feb. (2000–2022)	1000
Normalized difference between LST day and LST night	
Mean March–May from 2000 to 2022	1000
Mean June–August from 2000 to 2022	1000
Mean September–November from 2000 to 2022	1000
Mean December–February from 2000 to 2022	1000
Standard deviation March–May (2000–2022)	1000
Standard deviation June–August (2000–2022)	1000
Standard deviation Sept.-Nov. (2000–2022)	1000
Standard deviation Dec.-Feb. (2000–2022)	1000
Short-wave Infrared (SWIR)	
Mean June–August from 2000 to 2022	500
MODIS snow cover	
Mean snow cover	500
Land cover dynamic world 10 m near real-time land use/land cover (LULC) dataset	
Mean estimated probability of complete coverage by trees	250
Mean estimated probability of complete coverage by shrub and scrub	250
Mean estimated probability of complete coverage by flooded vegetation	250
Mean estimated probability of complete coverage by grasses	250
Mean estimated probability of complete coverage by bare	250
Mean estimated probability of complete coverage by trees	250
Terrain	
Profile curvature	250
Downslope curvature	250
Upslope curvature	250
Deviation from mean value	250
deviation from mean value	250
Elevation	250
Melton ruggedness number	250
Negative openness	250
Positive openness	250
Slope	250
Topographic position index	250
Terrain wetness index (TWI)	250
Multiresolution of valley bottom flatness (MRVBF)	250

References

Achache, J., Debeglia, N., Grandjean, G., Guillen, A., Le Bel, L., Ledru, P., Renaud, X., Autran, A., Bonijoly, D., Calcagno, P., Pluchery, E., Guennoc, P., Truffert, C., Rossi, P., Vairon, J., Avouac, J.P., Poli, E., Senechal, E., Brun, J.P., Galdeano, A., Diament, M., Tarits, P., Mercier, J., Paul, A., Poupinet, G., Marquis, G., Bayer, R., Chautru, J.M., 1997. GEOFRANCE 3D: l'imagerie géologique et géophysique 3D du sous-sol de la France. *Mém. Soc. Géol. Fr* 53–71.

- Angelini, M.E., Luotto, I., Rodriguez Lado, L., Mainka, M., Yigini, Y., Tong, Y., 2022. Global Soil Nutrient and Nutrient Budgets Maps (GSNmap) Phase I. Technical Manual. Global Soil Partnership. FAO, Rome. <https://fao-gsp.github.io/GSNmap-TM/step-3-mapping-continuous-soil-properties.html>.
- Antoine, P., Catt, J., Lauridou, J.-P., Sommé, J., 2003. The loess and coversands of northern France and southern England. *J. Quat. Sci.* 18, 309–318. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.750>.
- Arias-Navarro, C., Panagos, P., Jones, A., Amaral, M.J., Schneegans, A., Van Liedekerke, M., Wojda, P., Montanarella, L., 2023. Forty years of soil research funded by the European Commission: trends and future. A systematic review of research projects. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 74, e13423 <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13423>.
- Arrouays, D., Grundy, M.G., Hartemink, A.E., Hempel, J.W., Heuvelink, G.B.M., Hong, S. Y., Lagacherie, P., Lelyk, G., McBratney, A.B., McKenzie, N.J., Mendonca-Santos, M. D.L., Minasny, B., Montanarella, L., Odeh, I.O.A., Sanchez, P.A., Thompson, J.A., Zhang, G.-L., 2014. Chapter three - GlobalSoilMap: Toward a fine-resolution global grid of soil properties. In: Sparks, D.L. (Ed.), *Advances in Agronomy*. Academic Press, pp. 93–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-800137-0.00003-0>.
- Arrouays, D., Leenaars, J.G.B., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Adhikari, K., Ballabio, C., Greve, M., Grundy, M., Guerrero, E., Hempel, J., Hengl, T., Heuvelink, G., Batjes, N., Carvalho, E., Hartemink, A., Hewitt, A., Hong, S.-Y., Krasilnikov, P., Lagacherie, P., Lelyk, G., Libohova, Z., Lilly, A., McBratney, A., McKenzie, N., Vasquez, G.M., Mulder, V.L., Minasny, B., Montanarella, L., Odeh, I., Padarian, J., Poggio, L., Roudier, P., Saby, N., Savin, I., Searle, R., Solbovoy, V., Thompson, J., Smith, S., Sulaeman, Y., Vintila, R., Rossel, R.V., Wilson, P., Zhang, G.-L., Swerts, M., Oorts, K., Karklins, A., Feng, L., Ibelles Navarro, A.R., Levin, A., Laktionova, T., Dell'Acqua, M., Suvannang, N., Ruam, W., Prasad, J., Patil, N., Husnjak, S., Pásztor, L., Okx, J., Hallett, S., Keay, C., Farewell, T., Lilja, H., Juilleret, J., Marx, S., Takata, Y., Kazuyuki, Y., Mansuy, N., Panagos, P., Van Liedekerke, M., Skalsky, R., Sobocka, J., Kobza, J., Eftekhari, K., Alavipannah, S.K., Moussadek, R., Badraoui, M., Da Silva, M., Paterson, G., da Gonçalves, M.C., Theocharopoulos, S., Yemefack, M., Tedou, S., Vrscaj, B., Grob, U., Kozák, J., Advukla, L., Dobos, E., Taboada, M., Moretti, L., Rodriguez, D., 2017. Soil legacy data rescue via GlobalSoilMap and other international and national initiatives. *GeoResJ* 14, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grj.2017.06.001>.
- Arrouays, D., McBratney, A., Bouma, J., Libohova, Z., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Morgan, C. L.S., Roudier, P., Poggio, L., Mulder, V.L., 2020. Impressions of digital soil maps: the good, the not so good, and making them even better. *Geoderma Reg.* 20, e00255 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2020.e00255>.
- Arrouays, D., Mulder, V.L., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., 2021. Soil mapping, digital soil mapping and soil monitoring over large areas and the dimensions of soil security – a review. *Soil Secur.* 5, 100018 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soisec.2021.100018>.
- Augusto, L., Bakker, M.R., Morel, C., Meredieu, C., Trichet, P., Badeau, V., Arrouays, D., Plassard, C., Achat, D.L., Gallet-Budynek, A., Merzeau, D., Canteloup, D., Najjar, M., Ranger, J., 2010. Is 'grey literature' a reliable source of data to characterize soils at the scale of a region? A case study in a maritime pine forest in southwestern France. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 61, 807–822. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.2010.01286.x>.
- Azizi, K., Ayoubi, S., Nabiollahi, K., Garosi, Y., Gislum, R., 2022. Predicting heavy metal contents by applying machine learning approaches and environmental covariates in west of Iran. *J. Geochem. Explor.* 233, 106921 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgexplo.2021.106921>.
- Bishop, T.F.A., Horta, A., Karunaratne, S.B., 2015. Validation of digital soil maps at different spatial supports. *Geoderma* 241–242, 238–249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2014.11.026>.
- Biswas, A., Zhang, Y., 2018. Sampling designs for validating digital soil maps: a review. *Pedosphere* 28, 1–15. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160\(18\)60001-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160(18)60001-3).
- Blackford, C., Heung, B., Webster, K.L., 2022. Incorporating spatial uncertainty maps into soil sampling improves digital soil mapping classification accuracy in Ontario. *Canada Geod. Reg.* 29, e00495 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2022.e00495>.
- Bouassria, A., Bouslihim, Y., Gupta, S., Taghizadeh-Mehrjardi, R., Hengl, T., 2023. Predictive performance of machine learning model with varying sampling designs, sample sizes, and spatial extents. *Ecolog. Informat.* 78, 102294 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2023.102294>.
- BRGM - Centre Scientifique et Technique, 2014. *Indice De Développement Et De Persistance Des Réseaux (IDPR)*. Info Terre-Site Cartographique de Référence Sur Les Géosciences, Orléans, France (in French).
- Brus, D.J., Heuvelink, G.B.M., 2007. Optimization of sample patterns for universal kriging of environmental variables. *Geoderma* 138, 86–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2006.10.016>.
- Cahyana, D., Sulaeman, Y., Barus, B., Darmawan Mulyanto, B., 2023. Improving digital soil mapping in Bogor, Indonesia using parent material information. *Geoderma Reg.* 33, e00627 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2023.e00627>.
- Caubet, M., Román Dobarco, M., Arrouays, D., Minasny, B., Saby, N.P.A., 2019. Merging country, continental and global predictions of soil texture: lessons from ensemble modelling in France. *Geoderma* 337, 99–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.09.007>.
- Cerdan, O., Govers, G., Le Bissonnais, Y., Van Oost, K., Poesen, J., Saby, N., Gobin, A., Vacca, A., Quinton, J., Auerswald, K., Klik, A., Kwaad, F.J.P.M., Raclot, D., Ionita, I., Rejman, J., Rousseva, S., Muxart, T., Roxo, M.J., Dostal, T., 2010. Rates and spatial variations of soil erosion in Europe: a study based on erosion plot data. *Geomorphology* 122, 167–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2010.06.011>.
- Chen, S., Liang, Z., Webster, R., Zhang, G., Zhou, Y., Teng, H., Hu, B., Arrouays, D., Shi, Z., 2019. A high-resolution map of soil pH in China made by hybrid modelling of sparse soil data and environmental covariates and its implications for pollution. *Sci. Total Environ.* 655, 273–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.11.230>.
- Chen, S., Arrouays, D., Mulder, V.L., Poggio, L., Minasny, B., Roudier, P., Libohova, Z., Lagacherie, P., Shi, Z., Hannan, J., Meersmans, J., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Walter, C., 2022. Digital mapping of GlobalSoilMap soil properties at a broad scale: a review. *Geoderma* 409, 115567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115567>.
- Choi, K.S., Kumar, G.V.R., Kim, K.Y., 1999. Qualitative interpretation of Bouguer anomaly in the southern part of the Korean peninsula. *Geosci. J.* 3, 49–54. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02910234>.
- Ciesielski, H., Sterckeman, T., Santerne, M., Willery, J.P., 1997. Determination of cation exchange capacity and exchangeable cations in soils by means of cobalt hexamine trichloride. *Eff. Experim. Condit. Agronom.* 17, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:19970101>.
- Dong, W., Wu, T., Luo, J., Sun, Y., Xia, L., 2019. Land parcel-based digital soil mapping of soil nutrient properties in an alluvial-diluvia plain agricultural area in China. *Geoderma* 340, 234–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.01.018>.
- E.C., 2021. European Commission: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. EU Soil Strategy for 2030. Reaping the Benefits of Healthy Soils for People, Food, Nature and Climate. Retrieved from. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0699>.
- Faroux, S., Kaptué Tchuenté, A.T., Roujean, J.-L., Masson, V., Martin, E., Le Moigne, P., 2013. ECOCLIMAP-II/Eurol: a twofold database of ecosystems and surface parameters at 1 km resolution based on satellite information for use in land surface, meteorological and climate models. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 6, 563–582. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-6-563-2013>.
- Feranec, J., Jaffrain, G., Soukup, T., Hazeu, G., 2010. Determining changes and flows in European landscapes 1990–2000 using CORINE land cover data. *Appl. Geogr.* 30, 19–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2009.07.003>.
- Feranec, J., Soukup, T., Hazeu, G., Jaffrain, G. (Eds.), 2016. *European Landscape Dynamics: CORINE Land Cover Data*, 1st ed. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315372860>.
- Gallant, J.C., Dowling, T.I., 2003. A multiresolution index of valley bottom flatness for mapping depositional areas. *Water Resour. Res.* 39 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2002WR001426>.
- Gavrillescu, M., 2014. Chapter 17 - colloid-mediated transport and the fate of contaminants in soils. In: Fanun, M. (Ed.), *The Role of Colloidal Systems in Environmental Protection*. Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 397–451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63283-8.00017-X>.
- Gruba, P., Socha, J., 2016. Effect of parent material on soil acidity and carbon content in soils under silver fir (*Abies alba* mill.) stands in Poland. *CATENA* 140, 90–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2016.01.020>.
- Hengl, T., Rossiter, D., Stein, A., 2003. Soil sampling strategies for spatial prediction by correlation with auxiliary maps. *Aust. J. Soil Res.* 41 (8), 41. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR03005>.
- Hengl, T., Miller, M.A.E., Krizan, J., Shepherd, K.D., Sila, A., Kilibarda, M., Antonijević, O., Glušica, L., Dobermann, A., Haefele, S.M., McGrath, S.P., Acquah, G. E., Collinson, J., Parente, L., Sheykhou, M., Saito, K., Johnson, J.-M., Chamberlin, J., Silats, F.B.T., Yemefack, M., Wendt, J., MacMillan, R.A., Wheeler, I., Crouch, J., 2021. African soil properties and nutrients mapped at 30 m spatial resolution using two-scale ensemble machine learning. *Sci. Rep.* 11, 6130. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-85639-y>.
- Hiederer, R., 2013. Mapping soil properties for Europe - spatial representation of soil database attributes. In: EUR26082EN Scientific and Technical Research Series, ISSN 1831–9424. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, p. 47. <https://doi.org/10.2788/94128>.
- INRA, 2018. Base de Données Géographique des Sols de France à 1/1 000 000 version 3.2.8.0, 10/09/1998. Portail Data INRAE. Available online at: <https://data.inrae.fr/citation?persistentId=doi:10.15454/BPN578> (accessed: April, 03, 2024).
- Inventaire Forestier National, 2006. BD Forêt®. <http://inventaire-forestier.ign.fr>.
- Jamagne, M., 2011. *Grands Paysages Pédologiques de France*. Collection Synthèses. QUAE Editions, Versailles, p. 598 (in French). <https://www.quae.com/produit/1066/9782759210374/grands-paysages-pedologiques-de-france>.
- Jamagne, M., King, D., Le Bas, C., Daroussin, J., Burrill, A., Vossen, P., 1994. Creation and use of a European soil geographic database. In: In: 15th International Congress of Soil Science, Transactions, Commission V, Symposia, Acapulco, Mexico, vol. 6a, pp. 728–742.
- Jolivet, C., Arrouays, D., Boulonne, L., Ratié, C., Saby, N., 2006. Le Réseau de Mesures de la Qualité des Sols de France (RMQS). État d'avancement et premiers résultats. *Étude et Gestion des Sols* 13 (3), 149–164.
- Karger, D.N., Conrad, O., Böhner, J., Kawohl, T., Kreft, H., Soria-Auza, R.W., Zimmermann, N.E., Linder, H.P., Kessler, M., 2017. Climatologies at high resolution for the earth's land surface areas. *Sci. Data* 4, 170122. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2017.122>.
- King, D., Burrill, A., Daroussin, J., Le Bas, C., Tavenier, R., van Ranst, E., 1995. *European Land Information Systems for Agro-Environmental-Monitoring*. Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, Luxembourg.
- Kuhn, M., Wing, J., Weston, S., Williams, A., Keefer, C., Engelhardt, A., Cooper, T., Mayer, Z., Kenkel, B., R Core Team, Benesty, M., Lescarbeau, R., Ziem, A., Scrucca, L., Tang, Y., Candan, C., Hunt, T., 2023. R package caret: Classification and Regression Training. <https://github.com/topepo/caret/>.
- Kursa, M.B., Rudnicki, W.R., 2010. Feature selection with the Boruta package. *J. Stat. Softw.* 36, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v036.i11>.
- Lamichhane, S., Kumar, L., Wilson, B., 2019. Digital soil mapping algorithms and covariates for soil organic carbon mapping and their implications: a review. *Geoderma* 352, 395–413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.05.031>.
- Laroche, B., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Leménager, S., Arrouays, D., Schnebelen, N., Eimberck, M., Toutain, B., Lehmann, S., Tientcheu, E., Héliès, F., Chenu, J.-P., Parot, S., Desbourdes, S., Girot, G., Voltz, M., Bardy, M., 2014. Le programme Inventaire Gestion et Conservation des Sols. Volet Référent. Régi. Pédol. Etude et

- Gestion des Sols 21, 125–140 [in French]. <https://www.afes.fr/ressources/le-pro-gramme-inventaire-gestion-conservation-des-sols-de-france-volet-referentiel-region-al-pedologique/>.
- Lavallee, J.M., Soong, J.L., Cotrufo, M.F., 2020. Conceptualizing soil organic matter into particulate and mineral-associated forms to address global change in the 21st century. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 26, 261–273. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14859>.
- Le Bas, C., Barthes, L., Boutefoy, I., Fort, J.L., Scheurer, O., Darracq, S., Lacassin, J.C., Sauter, J., Schwartz, C., 2004. Utilisation des données sols d'I.G.C.S. en France: Un état des lieux. *Etude et Gestion des Sols* 11, 299–305.
- Lemercier, B., Arrouays, D., Follain, S., Saby, N.P.A., Schwartz, C., Walter, C., 2008. Broad-scale soil monitoring through a Nationwide soil-testing database. In: Hartemink, A.E., McBratney, A., de Mendonça-Santos, M.L. (Eds.), *Digital Soil Mapping with Limited Data*. Springer, Netherlands, Dordrecht, pp. 273–281. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8592-5_23.
- Lo, Y.-T., Ching, K.-E., Yen, H.-Y., Chen, S.-C., 2023. Bouguer gravity anomalies and the three-dimensional density structure of a thick mudstone area: a case study of South-Western Taiwan. *Tectonophysics* 848, 229730. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tecto.2023.229730>.
- Loiseau, T., Chen, S., Mulder, V.L., Román Dobarco, M., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Lehmann, S., Bourennane, H., Saby, N.P.A., Martin, M.P., Vaudour, E., Gomez, C., Lagacherie, P., Arrouays, D., 2019. Satellite data integration for soil clay content modelling at a national scale. *Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinf.* 82, 101905. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2019.101905>.
- Loiseau, T., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Martelet, G., Bialkowski, A., Nehlig, P., Arrouays, D., 2020. Could airborne gamma-spectrometric data replace lithological maps as covariates for digital soil mapping of topsoil particle-size distribution? A case study in Western France. *Geoderma Reg.* 22, e00295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2020.e00295>.
- Martin, M.P., Wattenbach, M., Smith, P., Meersmans, J., Jolivet, C., Boulonne, L., Arrouays, D., 2011. Spatial distribution of soil organic carbon stocks in France. *Biogeosciences* 8, 1053–1065. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-8-1053-2011>.
- Martin, M.P., Orton, T.G., Lacarce, E., Meersmans, J., Saby, N.P.A., Paroissien, J.B., Jolivet, C., Boulonne, L., Arrouays, D., 2014. Evaluation of modelling approaches for predicting the spatial distribution of soil organic carbon stocks at the national scale. *Geoderma* 223–225, 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2014.01.005>.
- McBratney, A.B., Mendonça Santos, M.L., Minasny, B., 2003. On digital soil mapping. *Geoderma* 117, 3–52. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(03\)00223-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(03)00223-4).
- McGarigal, K., Cushman, S.A., Ene, E., 2012. FRAGSTATS v4: Spatial Pattern Analysis Program for Categorical and Continuous Maps, Tech. Rep. University of Massachusetts, Amherst, MA, USA. <http://www.umass.edu/landeco/research/fragstats/fragstats.html>.
- Meersmans, J., Martin, M.P., Lacarce, E., De Baets, S., Jolivet, C., Boulonne, L., Lehmann, S., Saby, N.P.A., Bispo, A., Arrouays, D., 2012. A high-resolution map of French soil organic carbon. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 32, 841–851. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-012-0086-9>.
- Miller, B.A., Koszinski, S., Wehrhan, M., Sommer, M., 2015. Impact of multi-scale predictor selection for modeling soil properties. *Geoderma* 239–240, 97–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2014.09.018>.
- Minasny, B., McBratney, A.B., 2006. A conditioned Latin hypercube method for sampling in the presence of ancillary information. *Comput. Geosci.* 32 (9), 1378–1388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2005.12.009>.
- Minasny, B., McBratney, A.B., 2016. Digital soil mapping: a brief history and some lessons. *Geoderma* 264, 301–311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.07.017>.
- Møller, A.B., Heckrath, G., Hermansen, C., Nørgaard, T., de Jonge, L.W., Greve, M.H., 2023. Mapping the phosphorus sorption capacity of Danish soils in four depths with quantile regression forests and uncertainty propagation. *Geoderma* 430, 116316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2022.116316>.
- Mulder, V.L., de Bruin, S., Schaepman, M.E., Mayr, T.R., 2011. The use of remote sensing in soil and terrain mapping — a review. *Geoderma* 162, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2010.12.018>.
- Mulder, V.L., Lacoste, M., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Arrouays, D., 2016. GlobalSoilMap France: high-resolution spatial modelling the soils of France up to two meter depth. *Sci. Total Environ.* 573, 1352–1369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.07.066>.
- NASA LD, 2001. NASA Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center (LP DAAC) USGS/ Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center.
- Nowosad, J., 2021. Motif: an open-source R tool for pattern-based spatial analysis. *Landscape Ecol.* 36, 29–43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-020-01135-0>.
- Nowosad, J., Stepinski, T.F., 2018. Spatial association between Regionalizations using the information-theoretical V-measure. *Int. J. Geogr. Inf. Sci.* 32, 2386–2401. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2018.1511794>.
- Nussbaum, M., Spiess, K., Baltensweiler, A., Grob, U., Keller, A., Greiner, L., Schaepman, M.E., Papritz, A., 2018. Evaluation of digital soil mapping approaches with large sets of environmental covariates. *SOIL* 4, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-4-1-2018>.
- Pahlavan-Rad, M.R., Akbarimoghaddam, A., 2018. Spatial variability of soil texture fractions and pH in a flood plain (case study from eastern Iran). *CATENA* 160, 275–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2017.10.002>.
- Pahlavan-Rad, M.R., Dahmardeh, K., Brungard, C., 2018. Predicting soil organic carbon concentrations in a low relief landscape, eastern Iran. *Geoderma Reg.* 15, e00195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2018.e00195>.
- Pastore, G., Weig, A.R., Vazquez, E., Spohn, M., 2022. Weathering of calcareous bedrocks is strongly affected by the activity of soil microorganisms. *Geoderma* 405, 115408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115408>.
- Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Saby, N.P.A., Mulder, V.L., Laroche, B., Arrouays, D., 2017. Probability mapping of iron pan presence in sandy podzols in south-West France, using digital soil mapping. *Geoderma Reg.* 9, 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2016.12.005>.
- Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Chen, Q., Baghdadi, N., Chen, S., Gomez, C., Jacquemoud, S., Martelet, G., Mulder, V.L., Urbina-Salazar, D., Vaudour, E., Weiss, M., Wigner, J.-P., Arrouays, D., 2023a. Remote sensing data for digital soil mapping in French research—a review. *Remote Sens.* 15, 3070. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15123070>.
- Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Arrouays, D., Poggio, L., Chen, S., Lacoste, M., Bourennane, H., Minasny, B., 2023b. Hand-fee soil texture observations to evaluate the accuracy of digital soil maps for local prediction of particle size distribution. A case study in Central France. *Pedosphere* 33 (5), 731–743. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedsph.2022.07.009>.
- Román Dobarco, M., Orton, T.G., Arrouays, D., Lemercier, B., Paroissien, J.-B., Walter, C., Saby, N.P.A., 2016. Prediction of soil texture using descriptive statistics and area-to-point kriging in region Centre (France). *Geoderma Reg.* 7, 279–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2016.03.006>.
- Rossiter, D.G., 2023. Knowledge is power: Where digital soil mapping needs Geopedology. In: Zinck, J.A., Metternicht, G., del Valle, H.F., Angelini, M. (Eds.), *Geopedology: An Integration of Geomorphology and Pedology for Soil and Landscape Studies*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 171–184. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-20667-2_9.
- Rossiter, D.G., Poggio, L., Beaudette, D., Libohova, Z., 2022. How well does predictive soil mapping represent soil geography? An investigation from the USA. *SOIL* 8, 559–586. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-8-559-2022>.
- Saby, N.P.A., Swiderski, C., Lemercier, B., Walter, C., Louis, B.P., Eveillard, P., Arrouays, D., 2017. Is pH increasing in the non-calcareous topsoils of France under agricultural management? A statistical framework to overcome the limitations of a soil test database. *Soil Use Manag.* 33, 460–470. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.12369>.
- Safaei, S., Libohova, Z., Kládívková, E.J., Brown, A., Winzeler, E., Read, Q., Rahmani, S., Adhikari, K., 2024. Influence of sample size, model selection, and land use on prediction accuracy of soil properties. *Geoderma Reg.* 36, e00766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2024.e00766>.
- Six, J., Conant, R.T., Paul, E.A., Paustian, K., 2002. Stabilization mechanisms of soil organic matter: implications for C-saturation of soils. *Plant Soil* 241, 155–176. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1016125726789>.
- Suleymanov, A., Abakumov, E., Alekseev, I., Nizamutdinov, T., 2024. Digital mapping of soil properties in the high latitudes of Russia using sparse data. *Geoderma Reg.* 36, e00776. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2024.e00776>.
- Szabó, G., László, P., Takács, K., Szabó, J., Bakacsi, Z., Koós, S., Pásztor, L., 2019. Optimization of second-phase sampling for multivariate soil mapping purposes: case study from a wine region, Hungary. *Geoderma* 352, 373–384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.02.030>.
- Szabó, G., Pásztor, L., Heuvelink, G.B.M., 2021. Estimating soil organic carbon stock change at multiple scales using machine learning and multivariate geostatistics. *Geoderma* 403, 115356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115356>.
- Tifaoui, M., Guenet, B., Hatté, C., 2018. Large differences in global and regional Total soil carbon stock estimates based on SoilGrids, HWSD, and NCSGD: Intercomparison and evaluation based on field data from USA, England, Wales, and France: differences in total SOC stock estimates. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* 32 (1), 42–56. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GB005678>.
- Tziachris, P., Aschonitis, V., Chatzistathis, T., Papadopoulou, M., 2019. Assessment of spatial hybrid methods for predicting soil organic matter using DEM derivatives and soil parameters. *CATENA* 174, 206–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2018.11.010>.
- UE-SOES, 2006. Corine land cover. Service de l'observation et des statistiques (SOeS) du ministère chargé de l'environnement. In: Technical Report. <https://www.data.gov.fr/fr/datasets/corine-land-cover-occupation-des-sols-en-france/> (accessed 1 February 2024).
- UMR-LERFOB, IFN, 2008. Carte des pH de Surface des sols Forestiers. Données et Guide D'utilisation selon le Document Accord Agroparistech (umr lerfob) Ifn n° 2007-cpa-2-072. Tech. rep.
- Uuemaa, E., Mander, U., Marja, R., 2013. Trends in the use of landscape spatial metrics as landscape indicators: a review. *Ecol. Indic.* 28, 100–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2012.07.018>.
- Vašát, R., Heuvelink, G.B.M., Borůvka, L., 2010. Sampling design optimization for multivariate sampling. *Geoderma* 155, 147–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2009.07.005>.
- Viscarra Rossel, R., Chen, C., Grundy, M., Searle, R., Clifford, D., Campbell, P., 2015. The Australian three-dimensional soil grid: Australia's contribution to the GlobalSoilMap project. *Soil Res.* 53 (8), 845–864. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR14366>.
- Voltz, M., Arrouays, D., Bispo, A., Lagacherie, P., Laroche, B., Lemercier, B., Richer-de-Forges, A., Sauter, J., Schnebelen, N., 2020. Possible futures of soil-mapping in France. *Geoderma Reg.* 23, e00334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2020.e00334>.
- Wadoux, A.M.J.-C., Brus, D.J., Heuvelink, G.B.M., 2019. Sampling design optimization for soil mapping with random forest. *Geoderma* 355, 113913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.113913>.
- Wadoux, A.M.J.-C., Samuel-Rosa, A., Poggio, L., Mulder, V.L., 2020. A note on knowledge discovery and machine learning in digital soil mapping. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 71, 133–136. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12909>.
- Wiesmeier, M., Barthold, F., Blank, B., Kögel-Knabner, I., 2011. Digital mapping of soil organic matter stocks using random Forest modeling in a semi-arid steppe ecosystem. *Plant Soil* 340, 7–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-010-0425-z>.

- Wösten, J.H.M., Lilly, A., Nemes, A., Le Bas, C., 1999. Development and use of a database of hydraulic properties of European soils. *Geoderma* 90, 169–185. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(98\)00132-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(98)00132-3).
- Yamazaki, D., Ikeshima, D., Tawatari, R., Yamaguchi, T., O'Loughlin, F., Neal, J., Sampson, C., Kanae, S., Bates, P., 2017. A high-accuracy map of global terrain elevations: accurate global terrain elevation map. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 44 (11), 5844–5853. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL072874>.
- Zeraatpisheh, M., Ayoubi, S., Jafari, A., Tajik, S., Finke, P., 2019. Digital mapping of soil properties using multiple machine learning in a semi-arid region, Central Iran. *Geoderma* 338, 445–452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.09.006>.
- Zhou, T., Geng, Y., Chen, J., Pan, J., Haase, D., Lausch, A., 2020. High-resolution digital mapping of soil organic carbon and soil total nitrogen using DEM derivatives, Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data based on machine learning algorithms. *Sci. Total Environ.* 729, 138244 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138244>.
- Zhou, T., Geng, Y., Ji, C., Xu, X., Wang, H., Pan, J., Bumberger, J., Haase, D., Lausch, A., 2021. Prediction of soil organic carbon and the C:N ratio on a national scale using machine learning and satellite data: A comparison between Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3 and Landsat-8 images. *Sci. Total Environ.* 755, 142661 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142661>.